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A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON CARBON NANOTUBES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes are one of the most important fields in nanotechnology. Carbon nanotubes are cylindrical in shape with unique characteristics which makes them used in nanotechnology applications. Their various properties like surface area, strength, and stiffness which have led them excitement in pharmacy field. CNTs are classified into two type's i. e. single walled nanotubes and multiple walled nanotubes. For the preparation of CNTs there are various methods like arc discharge method, laser ablation method, and chemical deposition method. These nanotubes are used in diagnostic as well as medicine delivery system. It is important to be aware of the toxicities of carbon nanotubes due to their wide range of uses in medication administration and to learn how to deal with any issues resulting from toxicities. The biodegradation mechanism of carbon nanotubes has recently been the subject of numerous studies. The delivery of drugs using single and multiple walled carbon nanotubes has to be a safer and more efficient option.

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INTRODUCTION

A subfield of materials science known as nanotechnology uses chemical and physical procedures to create nanoparticles with certain desired features. More unusual allotropes of carbon, such as fullerene (C₆₀), fullerenes C₂₀, C₂₄₀, and C₅₄₀, carbon nanotube and graphene, carbon nanotorus, carbon nanobud, peapod, cup-stacked carbon nanotube, nanodiamond, and carbon nano-onions, were subsequently discovered in addition to the most well-known carbon forms, such as amorphous carbon, diamond, graphite, or lonsdaleite[1]. The best novel nanostructures are carbon nanotubes (CNTs), which are tubes with a diameter of less than 100 nm and are composed of the carbon allotrope graphene. Sumioliijima made the discovery of CNTs in 1991; at the time, the round carbon molecules were known as fullerenes[2-3]. CNHs have diameters that rise with length because the base of the ancone grows larger as length increases, whereas CNTs have relatively clearly defined diameters with manageable lengths[4]. Large, closed-cage carbon clusters known as fullerenes possess a number of unique qualities not previously seen in any other substance. As a result, fullerenes as a whole comprise an intriguing class of substances that will undoubtedly be utilised in upcoming technologies and applications. Before the smaller fullerenes C₆₀ and C₇₀ were initially synthesised and discovered, it was widely believed that these big, spherical molecules were unstable. However, some Russian researchers had already determined that the gas phase of C₆₀ was stable and had a sizable band gap. Fullerenes were found by accident, like with many other significant scientific discoveries. In 1985, Kroto and Smalley discovered peculiar outcomes in the mass spectra of samples of evaporated carbon. Here, fullerenes were identified and their gas phase stability was demonstrated. The hunt for additional fullerenes had begun [5].

Morphology and Structure of Carbon Nanotubes:

In carbon nanotubes, each atom is connected to three others, giving each connection a special strength. By merging together at high pressure and exchanging part of their SP₂ bonds for SP₃ bonds, nanotubes have the potential to form strong, limitless-length cables. Nanotube structure is depicted in Fig. 1[6].

Figure 1: Structure of Carbon Nanotube[6].

SWNTs and MWNTs are the two varieties of carbon nanotubes that exist. The pure SWCNT structure can be described as a rolled-up tubular shell of grapheme sheet comprised of carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal rings of the benzene type. A single atomic layer of crystalline graphite is represented by graphene sheets, which are seamless cylinders created from a honeycomb lattice. A MWCNT is a stack of concentric cylinder-shaped rolls of graphene. As a single molecule with millions of atoms, each nanotube can have a diameter as small as 0.7 nm and a length of tens of micrometers [7]. The SWCNTs typically have a tube thickness of just one atom and a circumference of only 10 atoms. Nanotubes can be thought of as almost one-dimensional structures because of their typical huge length-to-diameter ratio (aspect ratio) of roughly 1000. Larger MWCNTs are made up of numerous single-walled tubes stacked on top of one another. Only nanostructures having an outside diameter of less than 15 nm are eligible for the designation MWCNT; otherwise, the structures are referred to as carbon nanotubes. CNTs are different from carbon fibres, which are made up of strands of stacked graphite sheets rather than a single molecule[8-9].

LIMITATIONS OF CARBON NANOTUBES:

Since pure CNT (as manufactured, non-functionalized) are intrinsically hydrophobic, their inability to dissolve in the majority of solvents compatible with the biological milieu is the principal barrier to their use in biology and medical chemistry (aqueous based). Adsorption, electrostatic interaction, or covalent bonding of various compounds and chemistries that make them more hydrophilic are used to modify the surface of CNTs (functionalize them) in order to circumvent this issue. These alterations enhance CNT's water solubility and radically alter their biocompatibility profile. Additionally, the functionalization of their surface reduces the bundling/aggregation of individual tubes through van der Waals forces. However, significant restrictions still exist because it is difficult to produce batches of CNT with comparable properties, excellent quality control, and few impurities, making its use in pharmaceutical and clinical settings difficult[6].

GROWTH MECHANISM OF CARBON NANOTUBES:

Many people disagree on the mechanics underlying CNT creation. It is believed that in reactions using metal catalysts, carbon is first deposited on a catalyst NP, from which the C network eventually extrudes to produce a graphite tube. In situ electron microscopy has been used to examine this growth. The diameter of the tube is dependent on the size of the metal particle; SWCNT develop from metal particles with a few nanometers in diameter, whilst bigger particles typically result in broader MWCNT[10]Fig 2.

Figure 2: Growth Mechanism of Carbon Nanotubes.

METHOD OF PREPARATION CARBON NANOTUBES:

Arc Discharge Method:

The best-quality nanotubes are created using plasma-based synthesis techniques[11]. It involves two graphite electrodes that are passed a 50 amp current while being in the presence of helium **Fig 3**. Graphite vapourizes as a result, with some of it condensing on the reaction vessel and some of it on the cathode. The portion that is deposited on the carbon nanotube cathode. Co and Ni metals can be added to the anode if single-walled carbon nanotubes are what we're after[12]. A carbon-containing gas, such as a hydrocarbon, can be passed over a catalyst to create the carbon nanotubes. The catalyst is made of metal nanoparticles, typically Fe, Co, or Ni. These particles catalyze the breakdown of the gaseous molecules into carbon, and a tube then begins to grow with a metal particle at the tip[13].

Figure 3: Schematic Representation of Arc Discharge Apparatus[14].

Laser Ablation Method:

The Smalley group at Rice University first utilized a laser to create carbon nanotubes in 1996[11,13]. Plasma-based synthesis underlies all laser ablation techniques. These procedures use graphite rods, a catalyst mixture of 50:50 Co and Ni at 12000C, and argon flowing across it to prepare samples. In this process, metal catalysis the formation of single-walled carbon nanotubes while simultaneously producing a large number of byproducts. By chilling vaporized species, we can produce nanotubes[15]. In the plume of vaporized graphite, metal catalyst particles as small as nanometers are created. In the plasma plume, the metal particles promote the formation of SWNTs, but other byproducts are also produced. Small carbon molecules and atoms swiftly condense when the vaporized species cool to form bigger clusters, which may include fullerenes. The catalysts also start to condense, though initially more slowly, and attach to carbon clusters to stop them from forming cage structures. When catalysts adhere to cage structures, they may even open the cages. Tubular molecules develop into single-wall carbon nanotubes from these early clusters until the catalyst particles are too big or the temperature has dropped low enough that carbon can no longer diffuse through or over the catalyst particles. Additionally, the particles may get so heavily coated in a carbon coating that they are unable to take in any more, which would cause the nanotube to stop expanding Fig 4[13-15].

Figure 4: Laser Ablation Method [17].

Chemical Vapor Deposition:

Large-scale production and ordered synthesis are the two main issues with the Arc Discharge and Laser Ablation methods. Large amounts of unpurified nanotubes can be created using chemical vapour deposition (CVD). Chemical vapour deposition, in its most basic form, is the catalytic breakdown of hydrocarbon or carbon monoxide feedstock using supported transition metal catalysts.

It is carried out in two step process:-

- ✓ The catalyst is first applied to the substrate, and it is then activated either through heat annealing or chemical etching. An etchant is made of ammonia. Ni, Fe, or Co metal catalysts are employed.

The carbon source is then positioned in the reaction chamber's gas phase. Then, using an energy source like plasma or a heated coil, the carbon molecule is broken down to its atomic level. This carbon will diffuse toward the catalyst-coated substrate, and nanotubes will develop on top of this metal catalyst. Methane, carbon monoxide, or acetylene is the carbon sources used Fig 5. The range from 650 to 9000 C is the temperature utilized to create nanotubes. 30% is the average yield[13,16].

Figure 5: Chemical Vapor Deposition[17].

MECHANISM OF DRUG RELEASE FROM CARBON NANOTUBES: Properties of Carbon Nanotubes.

Chemical Reactivity:

Because of the curvature of the CNT surface, its chemical reactivity is increased when compared to a graphene sheet. The pi-orbital mismatch brought on by an increased curvature is directly related to the reactivity of carbon nanotubes. Therefore, a differentiation between a nanotube's sidewall and end caps is necessary. A smaller nanotube diameter causes more reactivity for the same reason. It has been demonstrated that sidewalls or end caps can both be chemically modified covalently. For instance, this method can be used to regulate the solubility of CNTs in various solvents. Although it is challenging to directly investigate the effects of chemical changes on nanotube behaviour since the samples are still too impure[18].

Electrical Conductivity:

Carbon nanotubes with a short diameter can either be semiconducting or metallic, depending on their chiral vector. The molecular structure, which results in a different band structure and consequently a variable band gap, is what causes the variations in conducting properties. The features of the grapheme sheet can be used to directly deduce the differences in conductivity. The fact that $n=m$ or $(n-m) = 3i$, where i is an integer and n and m define the nanotube, indicates that a (n, m) nanotube is metallic. It has been demonstrated that the length of the nanotube has no bearing on the quantum mechanical factors that affect the resistance to conduction[18].

Optical Activity:

Theoretical research has shown that when chiral nanotubes get bigger, their optical activity vanishes. As a result, it is anticipated that these characteristics will also affect other physical properties. CNTs may play a significant role in optical devices made using the optical activity[18].

Mechanical Strength:

In their axial direction, carbon nanotubes have a relatively high Young modulus. Because of its length, the nanotube is extraordinarily flexible as a whole. These substances may therefore be appropriate for use in composite materials that require anisotropic properties[18].

Thermal Properties:

All nanotubes are anticipated to have excellent thermal insulators laterally to the tube axis and very good thermal conductors down the tube, displaying a characteristic known as "ballistic conduction." At normal temperature, carbon nanotubes are expected to be able to transmit up to 6000 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹ in comparison, copper, a metal well-known for its excellent thermal conductivity, transmits 385 Wm⁻¹K⁻¹. According to estimates, the temperature stability of carbon nanotubes can reach 2800 °C in a vacuum and 750 °C in air. Unlike typical graphite fibres, which are substantially anisotropic, thermal expansion of CNTs will be largely isotropic. Composites made of carbon and carbon may benefit from this. Low-defect CNTs are anticipated to have extremely low thermal expansion coefficients[19].

Toxicological Consideration of Nanotubes:

Studies on the toxicity of pure nanotubes in cell culture have shown that CNTs are harmful to cells because of the oxidative stress that SWCNTs cause[20]. Compared to non-functionalized pristine nanotubes, functionalized and highly water soluble pristine nanotubes are less cytotoxic²¹. The effectiveness of CNT morphological alterations and flow cytometry analysis in identifying cytotoxic features has also been demonstrated. Additionally, the length of CNTs is related to their toxicity. CNTs are seen as superior possible carriers for drug delivery in the field of medicine. The toxicity that results, meanwhile, is poorly known and has a lot of room for investigation. The intrinsic toxicity of the surface and the high surface area are the two most important and common causes of the toxic effects of nanoparticles. Nanoparticles with a diameter of less than 100 nm are thought to have the potential to be more harmful to the respiratory system because they could spread from the site of deposition and circumvent normal phagocytic defences. Additionally, it can change the structure of proteins that trigger inflammatory and immunologic reactions, which may impact the normal function of tissues[22]. The presence of ferric impurities and the length of CNTs are often what cause the toxic effects of CNTs[23]. Physical form, structure, surface charge, surface chemistry, aggregation state, degree of functionalization, and purity of the examined samples are a few more factors that affect how hazardous CNTs are[24]. Additionally, the level of functionalization and the presence of functional groups affect how hazardous CNTs are. It has been demonstrated that a large-scale synthesis of unaltered, pristine CNTs contains contaminants including amorphous carbon and metallic nanoparticles, which can operate as another source of toxicity. According to a number of studies[25-26], SWCNTs can cause cellular responses by triggering oxidative stress-related molecular pathways.

APPLICATION OF CARBON NANOTUBES**Carrier for Drug delivery:**

The spherical CNT aggregates known as carbon nanohorns (CNHs) have an amorphous horn-like form. CNTs and CNHs have been demonstrated in research investigations to be promising drug delivery system carriers[27].

Blood cancer:

Leukemia is a cancer that can start in the bone marrow, which is the soft interior of some bones, but it typically spreads to the blood. Taghdisi et al. developed a tertiary complex of Sgc8c aptamer (this aptamer targets cancer of the blood biomarker supermoleculaminoalkanoic acid kinase-7), daunorubicin, and SWCNT named as Dau-aptamer SWCNTs to achieve Associate in nursing intensely targeted delivery of daunorubicin (Dau) to acute lymphoblastic leukemia. The tertiary complex was efficiently internalized into human lymphocyte cancer of the blood cells (MOLT-4 cells), but not into U266 malignant neoplasm cells, according to flow cytometric study. In a very mildly acidic solution with a pH of 5.5, the release of Dau-loaded nanotubes was pH-dependent. Dau was released from complicated after 72 hours at 37 °C, whereas the tertiary complicated of Dau-aptamer-SWNTs was relatively stable after a similar incubation at pH 7.4[28].

Breast cancer:

Invasive carcinomas are 20–25% more likely to develop when the human cuticular protein receptor type 2 (HER2), also known as c-erbB-2 or HER2/neu, is overexpressed. In comparison to the clinical medication formulation Taxol, Liu et al. tested SWNT administration of paclitaxel (PTX) into xenograft growths in mice with greater tumour suppression efficacy. The PTX coupled to PEGylated SWNTs demonstrated significant water solubility and maintained comparable in vitro toxicity to cancer cells as Taxol. SWNT-PTX enables PTX to circulate in the blood for a significantly longer period of time than Taxol and PEG-ylated PTX, leading to hightumour absorption of the drug as seen by an EPR test. The potent therapeutic efficacy of SWNT-PTX is demonstrated by its capacity to inhibit growth even at low medication doses[29].

Liver cancer:

For the cost-effective transport of antisense c-myc oligonucleotide (asODN) into the cancer cell line HepG2 cells, polyamidoaminodendrimer modified CNTs (dMWCNTs) were invented. ODN-dMWCNT composites were treated with HepG2 cells and optical maser confocal analysis demonstrated that they entered into tumour cells after fifteen minutes. These composites reduced the expression of the c-mycystron and C-Mycsupermolecule and hindered cell proliferation in a time- and dose-dependent manner. These composites outperform CNTNH-asODN and dendrimer (asODN) alone in terms of transfection efficiency and tumour cell inhibition[29].

Lymph Node Metastatis:

Yang et al. examined the potential therapeutic effects of gemcitabine-loaded magnetic MWCNTs (mMWCNTs) on gemcitabine-loaded magnetic-carbon particles in vitro and in vivo (mACs). The findings show that mACs and mMWCNTs, particularly when used in combination with high dose drugs and/or deep-seated in vivo magnets, significantly boosted GEM toxicity in vivo and inhibited lymphatic tissue metastasis. By combining the beneficial benefits of magnetic targeting with body fluid therapy, systems offer the possibility to increase therapeutic results and decrease negative effects associated with chemotherapeutic medicines. When administered subcutaneously while under the influence of a magnetic field, mMWCNTs-GEM were found to be superior to mACs-GEM in the no-hit inhibition of lymphatic tissue metastasis because of their super magnet behavior, which causes their magnetic moments to align on the applied field and result in web magnetization that significantly affects their interaction with the cellular membrane[30].

Gene therapy:

Gene therapy and ribonucleic acid have a great potential for anticancer treatment, and CNTs will transfer an excessive amount of therapeutic chemicals, including DNA and ribonucleic acid, to the target disease areas. The conformational structure and transitory conformational changes of DNA ribonucleic acid will be influenced by the wire produced structure (with a diameter matching that of DNA/siRNA) and excellent flexibility of CNTs, which can further increase the therapeutic benefits of DNA is ribonucleic acid. The in vivo mistreatment of siRNA sequences, which light-emitting diode to toxicity and necrobiosis employing amino-functionalized multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWNT-NH3+), for the therapy of a personality's respiratory organ malignant neoplastic disease model. This is thought to function biologically in vivo by initiating an apoptotic cascade that results in the deep necrosis of the human growth mass and a concurrent extension of survival for animals who are carrying human respiratory organ tumors[31].

Immune therapy:

Chemotherapy struggles with cumulative toxicity and drug resistance, but anti-tumor therapy occasionally has little side effects and intelligent patient tolerance, which has the ability to significantly improve the prognosis. Additionally, CNTs have demonstrated the ability to enhance the antigenicity of the proteins or peptides they carry. In a mouse model of the H22 liver disease, Xu et al. investigated whether MWNTs conjugated to neoplasm lysate supermolecule can improve the efficacy of an anti-tumor immunotherapy that uses neoplasm cell immunogen (TCV).

Biomedical applications:

Due to their advantageous characteristics, such as their high biocompatibility compared to other materials, quick lepton transfer dynamics, ultra-light weight, chemical immobility, high durability, variety of medication and antifungal properties, ability to act as macromolecule carriers, presence of exposed practical teams, etc., CNTs will find use in a variety of applications. They also possess semi- and golden-semiconducting qualities that make them a suitable material for a variety of applications, including environmental monitoring, clinical medicine, and food safety. Additionally, CNTs are crucial in the production of sensors for law enforcement use against a variety of infectious bacteria and aid in the treatment of cancer. Even yet, CNTs have a wide range of antibacterial activities[32-33].

Antifungal Therapy:

MWCNTs with functional groups attached were tested for their ability to inhibit the plant pathogenic fungus *Fusariumgraminearum*. The elongation and germination of fungal spores were inhibited by MWCNT with -OH, -NH₂ and -COOH fictionalization. Three times less germination occurred when MWCNTs were functionalized as opposed to when they weren't[34]. Additionally, research was done on the antifungal effects of different nanoparticles on the infamous fungal disease *Botrytis cinerea* on rose petals. At varying quantities (50 and 200 mg/L), MWCNTs, fullerene, and reduced graphene oxide were independently applied to water agar plates. According to the study, MWCNTs displayed inhibitory effects on fungus on rose petals at a dosage of 200 mg/L[35]. Another study tested the MWCNTs' fictionalized amino acid composition for antifungal efficacy. Results from 10 different species of fungi in the study demonstrated that lysine and arginine functionalized MWCNTs had stronger antifungal activity than virgin MWCNTs. The increased positive charge upon fictionalization is what causes the stronger antifungal activity. Because arginine has a greater positive charge than lysine, functionalized MWCNTs with arginine displayed marginally increased activity[36].

CONCLUSION

Scientists are only just beginning to explore the potential of these structures, and extensive study is still being done on the properties and characteristics of CNTs. The delivery of drugs using single and multiple walled carbon nanotubes has previously been shown to be a safer and more efficient option. The ideal method for producing carbon nanotubes is chemical vapour deposition since it results in highly pure carbon nanotubes. Carbon nanotubes are attracting the attention of researchers, who are anticipated to make further advancements in the near future.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVE

To improve the biodegradation of CNTs, further research is required to develop reasonably straightforward and acceptable methods of functionalization and characterization. This will assist to make them more biocompatible and non-toxic. To make CNTs more water soluble, biocompatible, non-cytotoxic, and optimally biodegradable, it is important to develop procedures for their functionalization and characterization that are moderately easier and more suited. Before creating CNTs for biomedical applications, it is necessary to comprehend their toxicological aspects. To maximize the advantages of CNTs, simpler methods for conjugating hydrophilic polymers or other bioactive substances must be developed. The safety issues and our efforts to make CNTs more biocompatible are essentially what will determine the future of CNTs.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

ABBREVIATIONS:

CNT	:	Carbon Nanotubes
Nm	:	Nanometer
NP	:	Nanoparticles
Amp	:	Ampere
Co	:	Cobalt
Ni	:	Nickel
Fe	:	Ferrous
SWCNT:		Single-walled carbon nanotubes
MWNTs:		Multiwalled nanotubes
CVD	:	Chemical Vapour Deposition
CNHs	:	Carbon Nanohorns
Dau	:	Daunorubicin
HER2	:	Human Cuticular Protein Receptor Type 2
PTX	:	Paclitaxel
asODN	:	c-myc oligonucleotide
dMWCNTs:		Dendrimer Modified Carbon Nanotubes
mACs	:	Magnetic-activated cell sorting
GEM	:	Gemcitabine
DNA	:	Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid
siRNA	:	Small interfering RNAs
mg/L	:	milligrams per litre

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